

A NOTE ON THE IODINATION OF A FEW HALOGENATED PHENOLS.

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Phenols and a few substituted phenols can be easily iodinated by means of iodine in potassium iodide solution in presence of concentrated ammonia or nascent nitrogen iodide (Datta and Prosad, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 441). In all these cases poly-iodinated phenols have been obtained. By similar methods *p*-chlorophenol, 2-bromo-*p*-cresol and 4-bromo-*o*-cresol have been iodinated, the first yielding 4-chloro-2-iodophenol (Buchan and Combie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 137) and 4-chloro-2 : 6-diiodophenol (Brenans and Girod, *Compt. rend.*, 1928, **186**, 1553; Joyce, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2643), the second yielding 2-bromo-6-iodo-*p*-cresol and the third yielding 4-bromo-6-iodo-*o*-cresol, the last two mixed halogen compounds having been obtained for the first time.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloro-2-iodophenol.—To *p*-chlorophenol (4 g.) dissolved in concentrated ammonia (20 c.c.), a solution of iodine (7.8 g.) in potassium iodide was added slowly with shaking and the products were allowed to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After filtration the solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a thick oily liquid separated out, which solidified slowly and crystallised in white needles (7 g.) from chloroform, m.p. 78°. It is easily soluble in alcohol and carbon tetrachloride. The *acetyl* derivative, m.p. 57°, is readily soluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and acetone. The benzoyl derivative melts at 83-84° and the picrate melts at 68°.

4-Chloro-2 : 6-diiodophenol.—A concentrated solution of iodine in potassium iodide was added drop by drop with constant shaking to *p*-chlorophenol (4 g.) in concentrated ammonia (20 c.c.) till the colour of iodine persisted. The separated 4-chloro-2 : 6-diiodophenol was crystallised from alcohol in white needles (10.5 g.), m.p. 108°. The *acetyl* derivative melts at 128°. It is also obtained from 4-chloro-2-iodophenol by a similar method.

2-Bromo-6-iodo-p-cresol was obtained from 2-bromo-*p*-cresol (4 g.) and

concentrated ammonia (25 c.c.) in the way described above. It crystallises from alcohol in shining white needles (6 g.), m.p. 46° . It is readily soluble in acetone, alcohol, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform, difficultly soluble in ether. (Found : Total halogen, 65.7. C_7H_6OBrI requires Total halogen, 66.1 per cent). The *benzoyl* derivative melts at 115° .

4-Bromo-6-iodo-o-cresol was obtained from *4-bromo-o-cresol* (4 g.) in concentrated ammonia (25 c.c.). It crystallises from chloroform in white needles (5.8 g.), m.p. 49° . (Found : Total halogen, 66.9. C_7H_6OBrI requires Total halogen, 66.1 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative melts at 40° and the *benzoyl* derivative melts at 85° .

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